

**PROBLEMS OF COMPARATIVE LITERATURE IN NATIONAL
LITERATURE**

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One of the tasks of comparative literary criticism is to study the process of influence and penetration of one literature into another and "to reveal in them those general historical and historical-literary patterns to which these literatures were also subject". Moreover, many prominent scientists of the XX century placed great emphasis on the need to study those literatures in which, for various reasons, whether it be geographical remoteness or national identity that has developed over centuries, whether it is historically established facts, the process of forming national literature differed from the pan-European one. Therefore, literary scholars of the mid-twentieth century emphasized the need to move away from "Eurocentrism" and form a universal world history of literature.

The subject of comparative literature is quite complicated even today, because as knowledge about the subject accumulates and the subject naturally changes, new tasks arise for scientists at each next stage of its development. Taking into account the fact that many diverse works are being carried out in this area, it is rather problematic to assume that in the near future it will be possible to talk about a single definition. The words of I.K. Gorsky (domestic literary critic, the main works are devoted to the problems of literary relations and comparative study of literatures, Polish literature, as well as deontology and the history of literary criticism) that only a lively discussion, an exchange of critical judgments can ensure the progress of thought. According to I.K. Gorsky, the consciousness of differences leads to the idea of looking for hidden similarities behind them ("it makes no sense to reveal the similarity of similarity)". Comparison of literatures, carried out in order to reveal their similarities, leads to the identification of specific features of each of them. According to many researchers, national literatures and their connections, as well as intra-national connections between the literatures of one country, regardless of whether they are created in dialects or in one literary language for all, can be considered the subject of comparative study.

In domestic literary criticism of the XX century, the concept of "national literature" is of significant importance, being associated with Soviet literature as multinational in form, which is gradually losing its former methodological

relevance. The reasons for this are not only in the change of the ideological paradigm, but also in the actual literary circumstances, which also underwent certain changes.

Therefore, for example, in Buryat literature, for example, rhyme, which, according to researchers, had a random character before acquaintance with Russian literature, starting from the 70-80s of the last century is gradually giving way to verlibre. This phenomenon is not connected with ideological changes in the country.

Fiction as a part of culture in its development reflects the growth of national self-consciousness, ethnic self-identification of peoples. Growing out of mythology, folklore, national literatures initially bear signs of ethnic systemicity, which is closely related to the formation of statehood, literary language, and their own artistic forms (medieval European sagas, Japanese haiku, Chinese xiaoshi, etc.). At the stage of formation of ethnic groups, the specificity and originality of national literatures are natural and inevitable.

Therefore, for the versification of the Mongolian peoples, to which the Buryat versification belongs, monophony is mainly characteristic, the uniform sound of the beginning of the lines is alliteration.

The term "national literature" N.I. Conrad uses it in a socio-historical sense: "as a designation of a certain social quality of literature". "National literature" is the literature that arises when a people reaches the level of a nation as a social category in its historical development.

Nevertheless, since the historical development of peoples is not a uniform process, the formation of "national literatures" is also different. The modern process of globalization is associated with a great variety of "national literatures". Among them are the "old", highly developed literatures of the European peoples, which have reached the level of the nation a long time ago. At the same time, the formation of other, "young" national literatures is taking place, i.e. formed as national relatively recently. These are, for example, Japanese, Armenian, Uzbek, Georgian literature.

In order to conduct research that is more effective some modern researchers believe that comparative literary criticism should be singled out as an independent section of the science of literature. "Being in dynamic interaction with a comparative analysis of the literature, it reveals a significant difference from the latter, both in the object itself and in the methodology of its study". However, such a question again comes from the problem of determining the main goals of science.

Today, it is obvious that foreign scientists have done a lot of work in the field of comparative literature (comparative studies), while in domestic science this area has begun to develop most actively only in the last decade.

The main provisions that domestic researchers have come to today are that the study of the world literary process is impossible without comparisons, without comparison, without studying literary influences, without analyzing the processes of reception and without referring to translated literature, without contact and typological relationships, and with the passage of time. Over time, these relationships become more and more diverse. A. D. Mikhailov (literary critic, the main works are devoted to French literature, literary theory, comparative literature and folklore) emphasizes that in the study of typological relationships, boundary, frontier eras are especially interesting, when old traditions collide with new ones over short chronological segments. "Based on the experience of foreign comparativists, K.A. Nurmatov drew attention to the fact that nowadays not only the comparison of two or more literatures, interpretations of certain archetypal, genre and plot structures in various literatures is relevant, but imagology is of particular relevance (images of national cultures in the interpretation of cultures outside of them) the so-called "dialogue of cultures".

Yu. G. Nigmatullina (domestic literary critic, the main works are devoted to the theory of literature, comparative and contrasted literary criticism, Tatar literature) regarding the differentiation of levels of typological commonality of literatures and the conditions under which these levels arise, distinguishes them in the amount of three. The first one is conventionally called ideological and thematic, which is characterized by elucidation of similarities and differences in ideological motifs, themes, images, genre features arising from the direct interaction of literatures that are in contact (for example, Uzbek-Russian or English-Uzbek literature). The second level is built on the basis of a specific historical and literary material, in determining the general patterns of development of individual national literatures, their typological similarities and differences. At this level, the category of artistic method becomes the basis for typological comparison.

The presence of contact links is not mandatory: typological patterns can be identified even in the absence of direct creative links between literatures. Only a typological commonality allows this or that literature to be included in the system of world literature.

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